

PRINCIPLES FOR THE PROVISION OF RETAIL SERVICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article examines the theoretical and legal foundations of retail services in commercial banks, ensuring the competitiveness of banks, analyzes the banking services provided to the population in banks, and develops recommendations.

Key words: banking services, banking infrastructure, banking product, remote banking, Internet banking, mobile banking.

In the era of rapidly developing “information technologies of the 21st century”, it is difficult to imagine banking activities without modern technologies. The use of modern technologies, the types of services offered, along with the reduction of banking costs, also saves clients’ time. It is known that banks are an integral part of the financial system and act in close connection with the market and the demands of producers. They are at the center of the world's economic life, connecting industry and trade, agriculture and the population, serving the needs of producers and consumers.

The most effective way to ensure the competitiveness of commercial banks is to gain the trust of customers and create all the amenities for them, as well as increase the type, quality and speed of service. To ensure competitiveness, banks feel a great need to introduce modern banking services and use new technologies. As a result of the increase in the standard of living of the population and the acquisition of modern knowledge, their needs for new financial services are increasing. Efficiency, quality, accuracy, safety and reliability of commercial banking services are the requirements of bank clients. Modern remote banking

services can meet these requirements.

In recent years, commercial banks in our republic have been trying to increase the types of services provided to their clients and diversify their activities through the development of retail operations. To this end, banks are actively introducing electronic service technologies, such as ATMs, mobile phones and remote management of their account numbers via the Internet. By introducing remote banking services, a credit institution, in addition to traditional operations, also uses new banking products that more fully and efficiently satisfy the needs of clients. But this is not enough, because in the era of rapidly developing information technologies of the 21st century in real time. There are a number of problems associated with the implementation of banking operations in the mode that are still waiting to be resolved. The expansion of the banking infrastructure in our republic serves to increase the competitive environment between banks, improve the quality and volume of banking services. Commercial banks are diversifying their activities through the development of new banking services, increasing the types of services provided to clients, which is the main factor in the emergence of modern information technologies and new banking products by banks, and, consequently, creating conditions for the development of the banking services market. The incomplete formation of a competitive environment in the banking services market affects the development of banking services. The relevance of the topic is determined by the presence of existing problems and the need to develop ways to solve them in terms of improving retail services provided by commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In modern economic literature, the definition of banking services as “mass operations” is widespread. But this definition does not clarify how services differ from other banking operations. Unlike a banking operation, which consists of collective actions of the bank aimed at achieving a single economic result, the banking service performs certain tasks that accompany banking operations⁵. E. F.

Zhukov divides banking operations into assets and liabilities and includes in the financial services of banks such activities as leasing, factoring, forfeiting and trust operations. Based on the above considerations, we considered that banking services are a set of technically related banking operations performed on the basis of a mutual agreement aimed at meeting the needs of the bank client.

A banking product is a set of interrelated services and bank operations that have a material form intended for sale on the financial market, i.e. a banking product is built as a result of a banking operation, and a banking service is part of it during banking operations. will be friends. Banking services contribute to the optimal execution of banking operations, and banking services, developed and sold together with banking operations, create a banking product. Modern banking services, currently used in world practice, are divided into credit, operational, investment services, as well as factoring services, leasing services, trust operations services, consulting and information services.

In the current period of rapid and intense development and fundamental changes in the economy, the digital economy and a number of advanced digital technologies are coming to our economy. Therefore, the leadership of our Republic has made a number of decisions and is developing a “road map” in order to further improve and facilitate the lifestyle of the population, computerization and further accelerate the development of our country.

Systematic work is being organized in the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan to provide electronic banking services to clients. In particular, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 12, 2020 “On the strategy for reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025” No. PF-5992 Modernization of banking services, creation of an effective infrastructure and activities of banks are considered as one of the priorities. Much attention is paid to improving the efficiency of the banking system through automation, as well as the gradual abolition of bank functions not

related to the main activity. Also creating the necessary conditions for the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies, automation of business processes of commercial banks, expansion of types of remote banking services; reducing the control load, including the load associated with improving the information exchange of banks with regulatory and government bodies, as well as simplifying and automating reporting processes; expanding the number and coverage of remote banking services, including contactless payments; widespread use of automated scoring systems, digital identification and credit pipelines; strengthening information security of banking data and systems; the introduction of new concepts and technologies in the banking sector (fintex, marketplace, digital bank)” indicates the relevance of the topic.

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